

Master's Thesis on Sound And Music Computing
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Measuring groove: A Computational Analysis of Timing and Dynamics in Drum Recordings

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For Maisy and William.

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Carlos Ruíz Zafón. 'La Sombre Del Viento.'

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Abstract

This thesis presents the implementation of a generative groove system, improving on currently available humanisers for electronic music production. This is achieved by complementing perceptual observations about rhythm and groove with the computational analysis of musical recordings of real-life drummers. First, an extensive literature review on rhythm perception, groove and groove generation is carried out and a working definition for groove is given. Providing additional downbeat annotations for the ENST-Drums dataset, we measure the micro-timing deviations from an idealised metrical grid as well as the amplitude fluctuations of three different drummers. These results are interpreted through various graphical representations and validated by a statistical analysis, making use of various machine learning techniques. A better understanding of each drummer’s behaviour on a sixteenth-step and beat-level is gained; furthermore, it is found that the genres of “disco” and “rock” can be characterised by their micro-timing deviations. We then design an algorithm for the generation of genre-specific micro-timing deviation patterns, which then trigger events in a digital drum machine. The resulting loops can be correctly classified, thus providing us with a proof of concept that we can better understand the generation of drum grooves and build more natural, multi-dimensional computer-based systems.

Keywords: Groove; Micro-timing; Dynamics; Music Perception; Drums; Electronic Music Production

Chapter 1

Introduction

*“What’s missing in this perfect world of grids, clips and quantization? Often it feels like a track is lacking a certain something, but it’s hard to put your finger on it. More often than not, the answer lies in the fine art of groove and swing. It’s the errors and inconsistencies that give a beat its vibrance.”*¹

Time is a fundamental dimension of life - and music’s temporal evolution is encoded in what we call rhythm. Groove is created in between, it is a feeling between the musician and their instrument, it is a feeling when the musicians of an ensemble interlock. Groove makes us dance, makes a musical performance memorable. Groove is not fortuitous, but linked to musical expertise: indeed, back in the 30s and 40s, during the height of the swing era, the expression “*in the groove*” referred to “*excellent*” and “*sophisticated*” jazz performance. Many jazz standards names reprise these ideas: “*Don’t mean a thing if it ain’t got that swing*”, “*Groovin’ high*”, “*I got rhythm*”, to name but a few.

¹Ableton advertisement text for James Holden’s Group Humanizer Patch: <https://www.ableton.com/en/blog/james-holden-human-timing/>

I believe that this high-level concept, whose complexity has thus far gone unexplained and undefined in academic literature, plays a major role in how we understand and appreciate musical experiences. This thesis' objective is to complement perceptual observations about rhythm and groove with the computational analysis of musical recordings and real-life drummers in order to understand more about the generation of drum grooves and create a program which is able to mimic these behaviours.

To some, it may seem alienating to computationally understand, bar model a “*feeling*” - isn't a feeling inherently human and inexplicable after all? I, however, believe that uncovering groove through a computational approach will improve our comprehension of the analysed music. Thus, on a personal level, this master's course in general and the project in particular has become the opportunity to question intuitions I have built over years of studying music from a traditional perspective, both at the conservatory and university. Moreover, it has allowed me to finally connect the dots between the two fields of my previous studies - music and mathematics, all wrapped in a framework of real-life applications: nowadays, where digital music tools - with an ever-growing community of amateur users - seek to unleash the user's creative potential, a need for computational models that make recordings feel more alive and human is born.

Scholars have stated that the two essential instruments for the creation of groove in beat-oriented music are the bass and the drums [1][2][3][4][5]. Furthermore, a strong relation between groove and body movements has been established [6][7][8][9][10][11], with the body movements linked to the evolution of the modern drum kit [12]. Therefore, I have decided to focus my research on the drums, the backbone of the rhythm section of modern popular music.

Scholars have also suggested that our subjective groove experience depends on familiarity and preference of the selected song's genre [13][14][15][16], thus I will be working with the ENST-Drums dataset, which offers more than 225 minutes of annotated tracks, presenting a variety of genres played by three different drummers.

In our work, we will focus on amplitude fluctuations and micro-timing deviations. Two rhythmic features of major importance, according to Iyer, who based the following statement on empirical observations of African percussionists: "*One might wonder how much emotion one can convey on a single drum whose pitch range, timbral range, and discrete rhythmic delineations are so narrow that the only two salient elements at one's disposal are intensity and timing. Yet it became clear over time that a great deal can be conveyed with just those two elements*" [12].

The structure of the remainder of this thesis is as follows. Chapter 2 provides the scientific background for the work presented in this thesis. We will review definitions about groove provided in the literature and present a survey of terminology related to groove and some of its defining features. Furthermore, existing hardware and software that feature groove and humanising functions will be discussed and relevant academic projects about analysing, transforming and generating rhythm will be listed. Chapter 3 outlines the methodology for the rhythmic analysis, which is performed on the ENST-Drums dataset in chapter 4. There, we explain the studies of micro-timing and amplitude variations in different genres by three real-life drummers and formulate hypotheses about their drumming styles and patterns. These hypotheses are then validated via a machine learning approach. Chapter 5 presents the implementation and validation of a generative groove system based on the previously generated results. Finally, Chapter 6 includes our contributions to the research field, a summary of the work presented, and a discussion of future work.

Chapter 2

State-Of-The-Art

2.1 What is groove?

At the heart of this chapter lies the question: What is groove? We will review the notion of groove and related terms in literature and conclude with a working definition of groove for future steps.

2.1.1 Why study rhythm and groove?

Common terms to denominate units of measures, serving as a framework for rhythmic analysis, are pulse, metre and beat. Describing the link between the latter two, Justin London states that metre *“involves our initial perception as well as subsequent anticipation of a series of beats that we abstract from the rhythm surface of the music as it unfolds in time”* [17]. Indeed, the *“perception”* and *“abstraction”* of rhythmic measure are the foundation of human instinctive musical participation [18]; Patel, referring to studies made by Buzsaki [19], even calls it *“reasonable”* to *“suspect that beat-based rhythmic processing has ancient evolutionary roots”* [20].

The ideas of anticipation and participation stand in line with physiological studies which have shown that listening to rhythmic sound sequences activates brain regions associated with reward and arousal [21], as well as regions in the motor system, even in tasks without any reference to movement [22]. Furthermore, experiencing rhythmic music is associated with pleasure, as indicated by self-ratings [23]. Coming back to the idea of performed rhythm, Honing argues that *“there is a noticeable difference between things measurable and things perceived in performed music. For instance, a meter cannot be directly measured in a performed rhythm – it is actually induced in the listener: the listener actively constructs [the meter] while listening to music”* [24].

Having established the importance of cognition in the study of performed rhythm, we turn our attention to three elements that Honing defines as the main components of rhythm: rhythmic structure, tempo/beat induction and timing [24].

Madison determined that *“intervals in the range 300–1,000 ms are favored for the beat”* and - at least in the range of 300 to 900 ms - that timing, or *“temporal variability in human performance”* is *“essentially a constant proportion (around 0.03–0.05)”*, thus *“nonlinear with respect to time.”* [25]. Expanding on this idea of non-linearity, Honing shows that listeners *“do not perceive durations on a continuous scale. Instead (...) expressive timing is only perceptible because there is categorization, the rhythmic category functioning as a reference relative to which timing deviations are perceived and appreciated”* [24]. In this same study, Honing treats the fundamental question on the relation between timing and rhythmic structure: in the just noticeable range of milliseconds, how long do we perceive a rhythm, whose inter-onset intervals are changed, as the same? Through a geometric reconstruction of the rhythm pattern, he observes that - as long as one rhythm is perceived - varying inter-onset intervals induce feelings of *“neutral”*, *“mechanic”* and *“swinging”* (figure ??)

Figure 1: Honing’s results on the relation between timing and rhythmic structure

These observations lead us to the assumption that variations in timing - even if in the range of milliseconds - have a big impact on our perception of performed music, inducing a feeling of "swing". In literature, "swing" and "groove" are closely related and often used as a synonym: thus, after a first look into perceptual and cognitive understandings of rhythm, time and timing, we will move on to the core question of this chapter: "What is groove?"

2.1.2 Terminology survey

a) Groove

"Swing" is sometimes described as a groove, pulse, or feel, and I assume that there are as many words for comparable concepts as there are musical styles, languages, and cultures." [26]

Literature fails to provide a consistent and recognised definition of what exactly constitutes these concepts of groove and swing. Iyer explains that the concept of groove has no analogue in rational language: "The fact that groove carries enough weight to override other musical factors in certain kinds of musical experience suggests that the traditional linguistics-based viewpoint does not suffice in describing the entirety of music cognition" [12]. However, characterising the fine art of groove and swing has been tackled in various academic papers, so in this section, we aim to review

the major points in the discussion around groove, to approach an understanding of *“the forces which give rise to and govern the groove (...) a key focus of centuries-old music theory as well as modern digital signal processing”* [27].

The first question to address is whether a single player has the potential to groove, or whether an ensemble is necessary. Zibowski says that *“a musical groove is most typically created by a small group of musicians working together, each contributing parts to the whole”* [1]. Zibowski and other scholars have stated that the two essential instruments for the creation of groove in beat-oriented music are the bass and the drums [2][3][4][5]. Furthermore, Iyer, in a previously mentioned quote, points out that the range of emotions that can be conveyed on a single drum is astonishing [12]. Taking this statement as well as the scope of this research project into account, we have decided to focus on the drums, the backbone of the rhythm section. Further studies into the importance of each instrument and the musical context for the creation of groove should be undertaken.

One of the most complete definitions of groove in literature can be found by Harmon, who defines the groove notions as *“periodicity (repetition at specific intervals), (...) variance (changes in loudness or timing), and (...) relatability (the groove has a natural-sounding or “human” element)”* [15].

One of the main recurrent themes in groove-related literature, however, is not that groove is a property of the sound or the music, but how it affects the listener: that is to say, body movement, quantifiable through physiological measurements. For instance, Sarroff states that *“the degree of groove is correlated with the degree to which the music induces the desire to move rather than the location and frequency of periodic entrainment”* [16]. In the same vein as this, Iyer [12] points out that the act of listening to rhythmic music involves the same mental processes that generate bodily motion; and relates to Janata’s crowd-sourced definition: *“groove is the aspect of the music that induces a pleasant sense of wanting to move along with the music”* [6]. Janata made over 200 young adult participants write definitions of groove in their own words and complete a survey containing phrases usually associated with groove. Madison, in his working definition, also confirms that groove is exclusively

linked to body movement: *“There is a quality of music that makes people tap their feet, rock their head, and get up and dance. For some music, such as jazz and various kinds of dance music, this is perhaps the most essential feature (...) groove, operationally defined as “wanting to move some part of the body in relation to some aspect of the sound pattern”* [23]. Davies explains that *“Groove is a central aspect of music perception and appreciation, closely connected to the main functional uses of music; namely, dance, drill, and ritual”* [7].

Janata [6] has shown that there is a direct link between body movement and pleasure: the higher the desire to move to the music, the more they enjoy it. From a physiological point of view, groovy music provokes a measurable response in the motor cortex of humans [28].

Musicians have agreed on the link between body movement and groove: it has to *“come from your body”* - some even believe that the inspiration for playing music stems from the pleasure of body movement [3].

Overall, this inner urge to synchronise body movement with the beat of the music has been described by musicians and various scholars [6][7][8][9][10][11]. However, as Danielsen points out, this sensorimotor coupling might not be mandatory for the experience of groove [29]. Janata shows that groove cannot be a simple function of performing a rhythmic behavior, as simple listening to music can evoke a groove experience [6]. In Kilchenmann’s study, they conclude that head movement was not triggered by a groove experience, but rather a compensatory mechanism, *“triggered (...) by the need to stabilize a rhythmically shaky situation”*, implying that groove is one but not the sole reason for body entrainment by the listeners [27].

The rhythmical structure plays an essential role in creating groove: Sarroff says that *“Music that grooves is characterized by strong repetition”* [16]. Keil believes that groove is not part of the composition, but something that is created interactively in the performance [2]. However, both Pfeleiderer [30] and Danielsen [29] argue in favour of a *“dual nature”*, so that groove refers to both a structure (represented by notation) and its performance, the latter one explaining that the groove experience results from

the “*interaction between rhythmic structure and the sounding realization(s) of that structure*” [29].

In order to create groove, the rhythmical structure needs a metric and rhythmic regularity [31], so that small violations of expectations such as syncopation (by varying the expressive timing) can create the inner structure of groove [12]. Sarroff points out that, by providing a “*temporal foundation*” and its repetition, groove “*is effective in engaging synchronization of bodily movement.*” [16] Thus, groove enables repetitive rhythmic structure to overcome its static and the music to “*sustain interest or attention for long stretches of time to an acculturated listener, even if “nothing is happening” on the musical surface*” [12].

Groove is considered to be highly subjective: indeed, groove has been found to have a correlation with preference, “*which might therefore be a likely confound of groove*” [6]. In literature, groove has been defined as “*central to the appreciation of many styles*” such as Jazz, Funk, Latin [7] and Samba [25]; characteristic of the “Black Atlantic” styles of music: jazz, reggae, rock [32], disco [29]; it has even been associated with classical music [33]. Iyer has put forward the idea that “*African and African-American musics value micro-rhythmic expression in part because of a cultural aesthetic that foregrounds the body*” [12], - considering micro-timing as a fundamental component of creating groove. Madison [14] adds the idea that our appreciation for micro-timing, implying our comprehension of groove, is also linked to the familiarity we have with a specific genre (more on this in the next two sections). Other micro-timing studies have investigated styles like Afro-Brazilian Samba [7] [34], Rock [8] [9], Swing [27] [35], Funk [7] [35], drumming from Brazil [36] and Uruguay [37] and Jazz [9][26].

In her book “*Musical Rhythm in the Age of Digital Reproduction*”, Danielsen finds herself one of the first to address the question as to what position groove finds in a quantised, digital world of music, but “*also earlier forms of groovy dance music that are characterized by a strictly metronomic organization of rhythmic events*” [29]. She argues that “*the ‘machine’ is not what it used to be. Its music can be deep and groovy or high-paced and frenetic; it can expose its mediating technology or conceal*

it; it can even evoke the human touch of the pre-digital era”, adding “the grooviness and expressivity of African- American-derived musical styles did not die with the new technology. Rather, they were reproduced and transformed.”

On the whole, it appears that styles linked to African traditions of rhythm are regarded as the *"grooviest"*. However, every genre, of both acoustic and electronic nature, has developed its own form and concept of *"groove"*, whose appreciation stands in direct relation with the familiarity and preference of the listener.

Another important point in how literature addresses groove is how to rate groove and groove similarity in experiments. In his 2012 study, Janata had participants answer the question how much the music *"grooved"* for pop music recordings. Using a slider, the results of ratings fit on a quasi-continuous Likert Scale. Janata [6], however, points out that asking explicitly about groove may create genre bias and hence favouring styles traditionally associated with groove. Madison circumvented this problem by falling back on the body movement argument and asking participants about how much the music *"evokes the sensation of wanting to move some part of the body"* [25]. Davies [7] and Sioros [10] used the same item for measuring groove. It falls in line with Sarroff who defined groove similarity *"as that aspect of the sound pattern that induces, within a subject, the desire to move in the same way"* [16].

To the best of our knowledge, three more groove rating methods have been proposed: Witek [11] collected ratings using a 5-point Likert scale (from 1= not at all/none, to 5= very much/a lot), whereas Frühauf [8] proposed a rating computed as a composite measure of five dimensions (the execution of timing, the performance in general, the felt entrainment/animation, whether listeners liked the music, and its overall aesthetic quality) on quasi-continuous 101-point Likert scales. Finally, in 2016, Senn proposed a new psychometric tool, the Emotional Assessment of Groove (EAG) questionnaire, where three dimensions were captured: *"listeners' felt Entrainment, Enjoyment, and the music's naturalness and flow, assessed by inversely measuring the degree of Irritation experienced by the listeners"* [35].

Groove is therefore a prominent topic in literature, yet the diversity of experiments

and attempts of finding correlates shows us that, although people acknowledge the existence of the phenomenon, their definitions and measurements vary greatly. The next part discusses the concept of micro-deviations, the most discussed possible feature of groove, before moving on to clarify the concepts of swing and syncopation, as they are often confused with groove [11].

b) Micro-deviations

A key idea of what induces groove has been the so-called micro-deviations, changing in timings in a repetitive rhythmical structure. Charles Keil was the first one to define the concept of Participatory Discrepancies (PD) [2][38]. In his original definition, however, the range of deviations was applied to more dimensions of music performance (pitch, timbre, dynamics), but most people nowadays adhere to *“small timing deviations from strict metronomic time, often within a range of +- 50 ms.”*

The theory of PD is widely accepted among professional musicians [3][4][39] and scholars (e.g. Klingmann [40]), adding to the appreciation of music performances [41], to an increase in aesthetic evaluation [42] and to the *“feel”, “groove”, or “swing”* [12] [43]. As we will see in the next section, micro-timing is also essential to humanising functions in commercial music software.

We have identified 16 academic papers and theses that investigate micro-deviations and how it is perceived by listeners: the complete table can be found in Appendix A. Some scholars, such as Prögler [26] have identified evidence for micro-timings in musical recordings. However, several scholars have put forward criticism towards the theory that micro-timing influences groove, which we would like to comment on. Butterfield [5] concluded from his experiments, where he asked listeners to distinguish between bass and drum lead in jazz duo recordings, that listeners had major difficulties identifying micro-timing deviations of 30 milliseconds or less or identifying which instrument played ahead of time; he claimed that the results offered *“little support for the central claims of PD theory”*, where we would claim that not perceiving the deviations does not necessarily mean that no groove was perceived. In Frühauf’s study [8], the participants ranked perfectly quantised rhythms higher

than the rhythms with micro-deviation: however, the deviations were artificially introduced into an otherwise perfectly quantised environment, thus conclusions on how it affects groove in musical recordings cannot be drawn. Moreover, Merker [31] has put forward the theory of “*exactitude hypothesis*”, which claims that groove is positively associated with timing precision. He argues that the PD theory is counter-intuitive, as micro-deviations obscure metric and rhythmic regularities rather than clarifying them.

Madison has put forward another theory which complements some groove ideas we talked about before: “*It is possible that appreciating micro-timing requires learning by repeated listening to a particular piece of music, or possibly considerable experience with music in a particular genre*” [14].

Micro-timing is omnipresent in musical recordings and may or may not be intentional from the musician. Most studies criticising the theory that micro-deviations positively affect groove creation fail to address the question in a natural-sounding environment, to use perception-inspired probability distributions as well as fail to acknowledge the existence of possible different patterns for specific micro-deviations.

c) Swing and Syncopation

The jazz historian Günter Schuller asserts that a rhythm is perceived as swinging - linking it to body movement that we defined as essential for groove - when “*a listener inadvertently starts tapping his foot, snapping his fingers, moving his body or head to the beat of the music*” [44].

The New Grove Dictionary of Jazz, Vol. Two, 1988 defines swing as follows:

“(1) A quality attributed to jazz performance. Although basic to the perception and performance of jazz, swing has resisted concise definition or description. Most attempts at such refer to it as primarily a rhythmic phenomenon, resulting from the conflict between a fixed pulse and the wide variety of actual durations and accents that a jazz performer plays against that pulse.”

Swing is commonly associated with jazz music and most studies presented here have dealt with jazz music, however, Waadeland [45] brings the idea forward that the “*life*”-bringing aspect of a swinging performance may be typical of “*musical performances belonging to other traditions.*” Many scores have an explicit marking to determine how the 8th notes are to be performed.¹

Various academics have taken on swing as a structural property: Waadeland retakes the idea of swing as “*a process*”, both for the individual musician and “*in an interactive context of playing together*” that makes “*a musical phrase, (...), a rhythm, or a melody “come alive”* by creating a performance that in varying degrees involves playing “*against*” a “*fixed pulse*” [45]. Honing and De Haas approach the concept from a more mathematical point of view, defining swing as “*a characteristic long-short subdivision of the beat*” with the subdivision effectively changing “*the ratio between pairs of notes from 1:1 to 2:1 or even higher ratios to give a sense of groove or swing*” [46]. Iyer points out that the interval of a pulse is “*divided (...) into two unequal portions, of which the first is slightly longer*” and states that the typical swing ratio - “*which tends to fall in the gray area between duple and triple*” - “*is strongly tempo dependent, typically lower for fast tempi and higher for slow ones*” [12].

The dependence of the swing ratio on time and beat duration is a controversial point in literature. Early studies have suggested a linear scaling of the swing ratio to tempo: Friberg and Sundström [41] found the absolute duration of the short note in the long-short pattern of the swing rhythm to be constant at about 100 ms for the medium to short beat durations. Honing and De Haas [46], however, show that except for beat durations of 250 to 350 ms, no linearity in scaling was found, but “*at longer beat durations the swing ratio seems to stabilize around a swing ratio close to 2.2:1.*” Thus, Honing [47] [48] has put forward a tempo-specific timing hypothesis, i.e. “*jazz experts adapt their timing to the tempo of their performance to obtain (or sustain) the effect of swing (...) as swing cannot be transposed in tempo by multiplying all durations with a constant factor.*” Furthermore, an analysis of three drummers’ swing ratio as a function of tempo was done by Collier and Collier [49]:

¹for instance, the free notation software Musescore: [https : //musescore.org/sites/musescore.org/files/swing0.jpg](https://musescore.org/sites/musescore.org/files/swing0.jpg)

they measured the swing ratios for a wide range of tempi, from slow (beat duration of 2400 ms) to fast (214 ms). One drummer showed a clear increase in swing ratio for decreased tempo, whereas the other two drummers showed a slight peak in the swing ratio in the intermediate tempo range.

A characteristic inherently linked to swing is syncopation, a “*rhythmic event that violates listeners’ metric expectations*” [50]. A way to add structural complexity, related to positive affect, it has been the centre of recent studies on groove by Sioros [10] and Witek [11].

The latter sees syncopation as “*large-scale, composed form of rhythmic complexity, broadly thought of as a shift of rhythmic emphasis from metrically strong to metrically weak beats.*” In a web-based survey, participants listened to synthesised drum-breaks with no micro-timing but varying degrees of syncopation, occurring within the bass- and snare-drum parts and had to respond the following questions:

- To what extent does this rhythm make you want to move?
- How much pleasure do you experience listening to this rhythm?

Witek found an “*inverted U-shaped relationship between degree of syncopation in drum-breaks and movement- and pleasure-ratings, indicating that intermediate degrees of syncopation elicit the most desire to move and pleasure in music associated with groove. As the syncopation in the drum-breaks increased, ratings increased accordingly, but only to an optimal point, after which a continued increase in syncopation caused decreasing movement desire and pleasure*” [11]. This resonates with previous research of Fitch and Rosenfeld [51], which showed that high degrees of syncopation prevent the perception of meter and thus a priori inhibit the building of metric expectation.

Sioros’ [10] work complements Witek’s study on syncopation, working with synthesized, monophonic piano melodies. Syncopation is systematically introduced via a computer algorithm, altering metrical positions only, no other expressive or

structural characteristics. Their first experiment shows that the syncopation transformations increased the groove ratings of the simple melodies, but also that all transformations had a similar effect. A second experiment was undertaken to see “*whether any kind of transformation that introduces faster metrical levels but preserves the structure of the melodies would in fact result in higher ratings from the metronomic deadpan original version, or if syncopation is indeed required*”. Two types of transformation were applied:

1. shifting note onset positions to introduce syncopation
2. density transformations that doubled the number of notes per bar in the melodies without introducing syncopation

The results of the experiment confirm the original hypothesis that the increase in the groove ratings for the simple melodies was particular to the syncopation.

Furthermore, Sioris states that “*the ratings show that a moderate amount of syncopation arising from notable salient instances of syncopation that underline the melodic boundaries contribute more to the perception of groove than a higher degree of syncopation that is uniformly distributed along the entire duration and does not relate to the melodic structure*” [10]. This is in line with Song’s research, who describes the concept of “*salient instances*”, e.g. how “*the location of a rhythm-component within the bar has a significant effect on perceived syncopation*” [52].

On the whole, we can establish that syncopation as a cognitive mechanism, in order to create rhythmic tension, can only occur in contradiction with an already established metrical pattern. Its possible relation on groove is location-specific, with a preference for metrically salient positions and intermediate degrees of syncopation eliciting the strongest desire to move in music associated with groove - but groove usually happens on a finer scale.

Other features

In the aforementioned study, Sioros points out that *“syncopation transformation have the inherent effect of creating a diversity in note duration as well as provoking a richer rhythmic structure in metrical levels”* which should be studied to see how it influences the perception of groove. Madison et al. [14] have studied the relationship between ratings of wanting to move and structural and acoustic properties of music associated with groove. Two of these five quantitative descriptors have been dealt with earlier on - systematic and unsystematic micro-deviations. The three remaining descriptors are:

(1) Beat Salience: designed to measure *“the degree of repetitive rhythmical patterning around comfortable movement rate”*

(2) Fast Metrical Levels: *“relative magnitude of periodic sound events at metrical levels faster than the beat”*

(3) Event Density: *“perceptual salience of sound events that occur at small temporal scales, faster than the beat level”*

In their study, Madison et al. [14] found that (1) and (3) explain *“substantially more of the groove ratings”* than the other three descriptors, however Madison stresses that this was their first attempt to study the correlations of groove and low-level audio descriptors - others could have stayed undiscovered in this study.

(4) Loudness - Amplitude - Dynamics: Harmon [15] argues that breakbeats causes *“exciting, danceable rhythms”*, because of syncopation, locking of drums and bass, as well as *“the nuanced fluctuations in loudness”*. He believes that this *“little variability in loudness”* next to timing makes for the discrepancy that can be heard between human breakbeats of jazz and funk and electronic grooves.

(5) Listener’s preference and experience: Madison et al. [14] state that the appreciation of micro-timing for groove ratings might require the listener’s experience with the respective genre and micro-timing style. Furthermore, groove is found to be correlated with preference, which might therefore be a likely confound

of groove.

(6) **Tempo**

So far, not much research on the specific relation between groove and tempo can be found. Most experiments on expressive timing and micro-deviations are done with music ranging on a tempo scale between 100 and 150 beats per minute. Furthermore, beat salience and event density are measured independently from tempo.

Finally, it is worth noting that especially the genre jazz showed the smallest correlations between ratings and descriptors in Madison [14]. This opens up an interesting question for this thesis: how and to what extent do genres contribute to groove ratings? Genre-specific studies are therefore needed.

As no recognised definition of groove has been found in literature, a working definition of groove for this thesis will be defined in the following section.

2.1.3 **Working definition of groove**

Groove is a complex concept, often described as a feeling, as we fail to fully describe it in words. There are certain contexts, which have a higher likelihood of inducing groove: an ensemble with a drum and bass combination at its core as well as Afro-American genres, however, groove is not restricted to a particular instrument nor a specific genre - actually, the feeling of groove seems to be unique for each musician, rhythmical pattern or genre. And yet, there appears to be a fundamental idea behind all types of groove: a periodicity, i.e. a stable metre and pulse, has to be established to build a sense of structure, so that our expectations can be violated and thus create a unique tension in repetition. Compared to syncopation, whose violations of the pulse and the metrical subdivisions can be notated in the score, groove as a violator acts on a much finer scale, in the range of milliseconds. An overall feeling of push and pull, which makes the music feel alive and human, is created and is reflected on various levels, from micro-timing deviations to body movement. As the predominant factors of variance, we have identified changes in timing and in dynamics / loudness (however, given that groove is a complex phenomenon, further

factors such as timbre, pitch, instrument interlocking, syncopation, fast metrical levels, event density and tempo could be investigated). Furthermore, groove is a subjective phenomenon and its experience depends on the listener's preference and familiarity with the genre. In order to rate the groove experience, its entrainment of body movement is an important, although not a necessary factor.

Combining our findings from the state-of-the-art review, we conclude with the following working definition for groove:

Groove arises when micro-timing deviations and amplitude fluctuations sustain our interest in repetitive music and elicit a desire to dance. Groove is not confined to a genre or an instrument, but its experience greatly depends on the listener.

2.2 Review of existing groove and humaniser hardware and software

“If you’re comparing a drum machine to a master drummer I would be one of those who argue that drum machines and quantization don’t have the same feel as a real drummer. But I don’t think most people use drum machines to replace history’s great drummers. They use drum machines to create a particular looped groove that works well in a particular musical context, with full knowledge that the drum machine won’t respond in dynamics or tempo to the other musicians, won’t spontaneously think of creative and complimentary drum parts drawn from a lifetime knowledge of thousands of recordings, and won’t produce subtly-nuanced percussive timbres by tapping, rubbing and bending a drum in hundreds of possible ways.” – Roger Linn²

In the last section we established a working definition of groove, now we will review existing hardware and software that deals with groove - or as in this domain more often referred to as quantisation and humanising functions - from a music production point of view.

2.2.1 Hardware

With the advent of dedicated drum machines, samplers and grooveboxes, the *"swing"* function was introduced in Roger Linn’s 1979 LM-1 Drum Computer in order to emulate a human feel when using quantized beats. This new production workflow ended up having a massive impact on hip hop and electronic music from the early 80s. The LM-1’s manual describes the then-called *"shuffle"* function as seen in figure 2.

Linn quantises each drum beat to the nearest step and then delays the playback of every other step in the sequencer. The system uses percentages to express the

²Interview with Roger Linn in Attack Magazine: "Roger Linn on swing, groove and the magic of the MPC’s timing" <https://www.attackmagazine.com/features/interview/roger-linn-swing-groove-magic-mpc-timing/3/>

Figure 2: The definition of the shuffle function in Linn's Manual

amount of swing applied to every second step. 50 percent refers to straight timing, so both 16th in the 8th have equal timing. 66 percent would be a perfect triplet swing. The LM-1 had a sequencer solution of 48 parts per quarter note and thus permits swing variations of 50, 54, 58, 60, 62, 66, 70 and 75.

Drum machine pioneer Roger Linn went on to design Akai's famous MPC series (Midi Production Center), still "*considered to be among the best around when it comes to groove and timing*"³. In an extensive interview with Attack Magazine, Linn states that six factors (listed in order of importance) have contributed to natural, human-feeling grooves in his drum machines, with swing, applied to quantised 16th-note beats being his number one - next to natural dynamic response on drum pads and pressure-sensitive note repeat.

Linn's approach to swing can be found in hardware such as the DSI Tempest and E-Mu SP-1200 (as seen in figure 3) as well as Digital Audio Workstations including Logic and Reason, which will be our next topic.

³Attack Magazine: <https://www.attackmagazine.com/features/interview/roger-linn-swing-groove-magic-mpc-timing/>

(a) found in DSI Tempest manual

(b) found in E-Mu SP-1200 manual

Figure 3: Linn's approach to swing in hardware

Figure 4: The swing function in Apple Logic

2.2.2 Software

a) DAW: Apple Logic

As mentioned above, logic uses the same six-setting convention as Linn for defining the swing function: 16A: 50percent (straight timing), 16B: 54, 16C: 58, 16D: 62, 16E: 66, 16F: 71.

Figure 4 illustrates the effect the six different settings have on the timing of the sixteenth notes, from 16A (top) to 16F (bottom).

The Apple software offers further parameters for advanced quantisation: Q-Strength, Q-Range, Q-Flam, Q-Velocity, Q-Length.

Furthermore, a "Transform / Humanise function" for MIDI is available, randomising the position and velocity of MIDI events.

Figure 5: The swing function in Native Instrument's Maschine

b) DAW: ProTools

ProTools offers a swing function, where the user first chooses whether it is applied to 8th or 16th notes, then chooses the strength of the effect on a scale from 0 to 100 (straight timing to triplet swing feel). Any value between 100 and 150 makes that the events move beyond the triplet feel into the next 16th-note boundary. Secondly, quantisation is made possible by using the Beat Detective function and then applying the quantise function with the following parameters: note on, note off, quantise grid, randomise grid, swing, strength, range.

c) DAW: Native Instrument's Maschine

Native Instruments' Maschine's swing function (figure 5) can be applied to groups or individual sounds in a project. Controllable parameters are: amount of swing (from 0 to 100), cycles and groove inversion (to move the sample to the left or to the right from the mathematical exact position).

Figure 6: The group humaniser in Ableton

d) DAW: Ableton Live

Ableton Live offers groove quantisation that can read imported audio, MIDI, and groove template files. Their so-called groove pool offers various groove templates, creating sounds of various existing hardware sequencers and drum machines (the Akai MPC, for instance). Control parameters are base, quantise and timing. Furthermore, the musician James Holden has developed MaxForLive devices "*Group Humanizer*", based on Holger Hennig's research [53] and seen in figure 6, which are able to "*to inject a realistic timing into multiple computer generated parts, as if they were being played by musicians performing together. It can even listen to input from a real musician and respond to his or her timing errors in a natural manner.*"

We have seen that swing and groove systems derived from Linn are fixed, making periodic deformations of the grid, whereas Hennig and Holden's devices rely on a stochastic process, using a pink noise distribution for micro-deviations. The latter approach seems more appropriate as we have established the inherent variability in human repetitive actions, especially at a micro-timing level.

e) Group Humanizer

The researcher whose models James Holden used to create the "*Group Humanizer*" published an open-source script on GitHub with a humanising function. Hennig states that it "*only reproduces the generic timing of humans and does not cover delays or other features that are introduced by musicians by intention e.g. to interpret a musical piece.*"

Four major parameters can be controlled, their default setting being values that have been determined for professional musicians:

- **humanising type:** exact, group humanise (Coupling the time series using two-component ARFIMA process), Humanize drum and bass with the same deviations (default setting), Humanize drum and bass separately, Group humanize (Coupling the time series using MICS model)
- **alpha:** strength of correlations between errors ($1/f^{\alpha}$). The larger the alpha value, the stronger the dependence of an error on previous errors. A range of $0.3 < \alpha < 1.4$ was found in experiments.
- **sigma:** standard deviation of the introduced delays of the notes in milliseconds (default setting: 10 milliseconds)
- **seed:** The Humanizer is based on stochastic models. In order to repeat a humanisation, a seed can be specified.

2.2.3 Critical Review

Based on this small review on existing groove and humanising functions available in hard- and software, two main critique points can be formulated:

- **unattractive and non-intuitive visual representation:**
Groove styles as in Ableton, for instance, are presented in an unaesthetic and unintuitive click-through menu, alphabetically ordered, of the different groove style. The groove, swing and humanising functions provide a limiting set of parameters - the actual function often being presented on a one-dimensional scale from 0 to 100. This makes for an unattractive and non-intuitive visual representation of the aforementioned functions.

- **cross-section of industry and academia:**

The solutions proposed by the industry are often not grounded in perceptual actualities and have offsets created by random number generators or white-noise functions. Methods proposed in literature are computationally complex and expensive, thus the industry opts to ignore existing musical correlations (with the exception of Ableton’s Group Humanizer). As mentioned by Bilmes [43], many approaches to improve systems could be implemented: velocity of individual drum hits, negative swing, attack / decay of hits, to name but a few.

The next section will have a more extensive look at how academia has tackled the problem of analysing, transforming and generating musical recordings so far.

2.3 Review of Analysis, Transformation and Generation of Musical Recordings

2.3.1 Rhythmic analysis

Onset detection algorithms are a fundamental tool for rhythmic analysis. The detection of percussive onsets is considered as solved by Böck and Widmer [54]; at Mirex competition 2016, most algorithms applied to solo drums scored higher than 85 in F-Measure. Current state-of-the-art approaches are based on spectral flux onset detection algorithm. Sebastian Böck’s SuperFlux [54] is widely recognised as the best implementation available as open source, apt for both offline and online real-time situations. It is based on the non-probabilistic LogFiltSpecFlux method, enhanced by a vibrato suppression filter. This is done by detecting positive changes over time, but *“instead of calculating the difference from the same bin of a previous frame it includes a special trajectory-tracking stage”* [54].

In his master’s thesis from 1993, Jeffrey Bilmes [43] was one of the first authors to present algorithms *“that computers can use to produce expressive sounding rhythmic phrases”*; thus opening the ground for a quantitative description *“of the many*

elusive human behaviors.” Since then, many algorithms have been proposed to automatically estimate tempo, beat and swing (e.g. Laroche [55]), which all underly the importance of rhythmic analysis as formulated by Bilmes.

2.3.2 Automatic transformation of rhythm in audio signals

Systems for automatic transformation of rhythm in audio signals generally follow three steps of implementation: analysis (as mentioned above), transformation and reconstruction. We’ll present four systems meeting different ends:

a) Changing the swing [56]

In 2003, Guoyon [56] argued that existing software implementations for swing modification failed to be fully automatic, either a sample library had to be bought or complex signals caused poor sound quality. The authors thus presented a system for polyphonic musical audio signals that lets users modify both the swing ratio and factor. The analysis part consisted of determining two distinct metrical level (thanks to onset detection, tick period determination and eighth and quarter-note period determination) as well as estimating the swing ratio deduced from IOI histogram computation. In the transformation stage, onsets were moved from their original positions with a time-scale factor (expansion and compression). In the case of the time-scale factor being above 1.3, phasing and flanging effects appear during the reconstruction phase, which, the authors describe, is mainly a phase-locked vocoder, based on transient detection.

b) Groovator: Changing swing, tempo, accent and meter [57]

Similarly, Bonada and Janer [57] presented the groovator, a real-time VST plug-in for rhythm transformations of polyphonic audio signals. The analysis algorithm is based on Guoyon [58], making use of perceptual frequency bands and a half-wave rectifier. In the transformation stage, tempo - for which MIDI is required - is controlled by a time-scaling factor proposed by Bonada [59] and swing as detailed in part (A). Two simple approaches have been used: for metre transformation, the

last quarter-note of the bar is either repeated or deleted; for accent transformation a bass-booster is used. No reconstruction stage is specified.

c) Loopalooza: Real-time manipulation of syncopation [60]

Cocharro et al. [60] have developed the real-time MaxForLive device *"Loopalooza"*, *"a system that estimates and manipulates rhythmic structures from audio loops (...) to perform syncopation transformations."* The analysis stage uses the MaxMSP-external `fzero` for onset detection, in order to *"extract the rhythmic structure in the context of a known time signature and tempo"* (retrieved by Ableton Live). Transformation is done by manipulating the syncopation in symbolic data by displacing the start times of the onsets with respect to a metrical template, an algorithm previously developed and called Syncopalooza algorithm by Sioros. Finally, to cope with silent gaps and overlapping segments resulting from onset displacement, two reconstruction approaches are proposed: first, time-scaling, *"automatically [adjusting] the duration of the events to the transformed inter onset intervals"*, resulting in blurred sharpness of percussive events or distorted rhythmic patterns. The second approach - preferred by the authors - considers resampling the musical events combined with a fade-out envelope to fill the gaps. Finally, it is worth noting that Loopalooza circumvents problems linked to automated onset detection in polyphonic systems as only the detection of the most salient events is needed for syncopation.

d) Matching rhythm of the audio input to a model [61]

Another application for rhythm transformation, this time related to timbre, has been presented by Ravelli. Their system enables the user to select an original loop and a model loop, *"whose rhythmic pattern the user wants recreated"* [61]. The rhythm analysis, matching and transformation is fully automated and by-passes MIDI sequencing.

2.3.3 Non-automated drum analysis

Two non-automated novel methods have featured as recent contribution for analysing groove in relation to drums:

In the first, Räsänen analyses fluctuations of hi-hat timing and dynamics in Jeff Porcaro’s drumming in “*I Keep Forgettin’*” [62]. By using highly sensitive onset detection (to one millisecond precision) and time series analysis to study the amplitude and temporal fluctuations, they find that fluctuations of hi-hat amplitudes and interbeat intervals (times between hits) have clear long-range correlations and short-range anti-correlations separated by a characteristic time scale. In addition, they are able to detect subtle features in Porcaro’s drumming such as small drifts in the 16th note pulse and non-trivial periodic two-bar patterns in both hi-hat amplitudes and intervals.

The second method, proposed by Harmon, relies on “*time-series methodology, applied to datasets of the amplitude of music signals*” [15]. Harmon resamples the recordings of breakbeats to discrete-time signal processing for musical analysis. Then, he calculates the autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation functions for the drums, as well as the cross-correlation between drums and bass, before an exploratory analysis of the frequency spectrum for the drum amplitude. In the next step, a moving-maximum resampling algorithm is applied. The author then proposes a seasonal autoregressive integrated moving-average model with explanatory variables, which, as the author argues, can be used for a robust modeling of “*humanization*” of electronic instruments.

2.3.4 Generation: rhythm

In a recent study, Elmslay et al. [63] explore models following the “*interplay between metric perception, expectational prediction, and rhythmic production with respect to expressive variations on musical timing.*” In order to achieve this, two neural network models are combined: a gradient frequency neural network (GFNN) which pictures the perception layer, by “*resonating nonlinearly with the musical input, creating*

a hierarchy of strong and weak oscillations that relate to the metrical structure.”

A Long Short-Term Memory Neural Network (LSTM) forms the prediction layer, foretelling long-term dependencies in the time-series. So after an input of initial values, new expressive timing structures are generated and can compete with state-of-the-art methods for symbolic data.

2.3.5 Generation: humanised drum patterns

A number of humanisation algorithms and rhythm generation approaches have been proposed in literature. This paragraph attempts to sum up the most promising proposals:

A first step towards systematic humanisation was done by Wright and Berdahl who applied supervised machine learning to Brazilian drumming in order to predict micro-timing deviation schemes [36]. Through this approach, which the authors state is *“easily adaptable to other forms of music”*, they manage to uncover certain characteristics of the genre. However, the generated output stills needs improvement. The Gaussian Processes Regression technique appeared to be the most promising method.

In 2014, Stables proposed a model for multi-player micro-timing humanisation, using a multivariate Markov Model [64]. In this model, which *“alleviates the phase issues that arise when humanisation algorithms are applied to multiple sequences simultaneously”*, parameters are derived from a corpus of multi-performer musical data, modulations are applied probabilistically to the different sequences. Furthermore, dependencies between players are estimated using a lagged cross-correlation metric. The authors achieved an improvement of 21.94 percent accuracy for naturalness of expression, yet human sequences were still perceived as more expressive.

This research was based on a previous paper by Stables [65], one of two recent papers that deal explicitly with drum pattern humanisation: in his paper from 2012, Stables derives prior and likelihood functions from a dataset of professional drummers *“to create a series of empirical distributions”*, which are then used to modulate

onset locations and amplitudes, using a recursive Bayesian framework. The author then demonstrates that for a 4/4 rock beat at 120 bpm, the probabilistic model has a better performance than Gaussian models, at the core of many humanisation algorithms.

A second approach, based on fuzzy logic, was put forward by Liam O’Sullivan [66], thought of as a “*first step*” towards building a humaniser. The system automatically modifies the strike velocity of a programmed MIDI drum pattern.

2.4 Conclusions: Working definition and Hypothesis

Scholars have yet to agree on a definition of groove, however, we were able to identify several essential constituents: inducing body movement and desire to dance, a dependence of the listener’s familiarity and preference of genres, periodicity and repetition of rhythmic structures, dynamics, violation of timing expectation on a fine scale in the range of milliseconds. Commercial software often fails to mirror the complexity of the phenomenon; its humanising functions rely either on a fixed system or a better, stochastic approach to micro-timing. In academia, the first interesting steps have been made to analyse musical recordings and draw conclusions on the drummer’s behaviour, focusing on both micro-timing and dynamics.

As previously stated, we have arrived at the following working definition for this thesis:

Groove arises when micro-timing deviations and amplitude fluctuations sustain our interest in repetitive music and elicit a desire to dance. Groove is not confined to a genre or an instrument, but its experience greatly depends on the listener.

The instrument of our choice for this project are the drums, which have been identified as essential for the creation of groove in beat-oriented music [3] [2] [4]. Iyer defined micro-timing and amplitude variance as the two predominant features to convey emotions - both factors were also the centre of an extensive analysis by

Räsänen. Furthermore, this state-of-the-art has identified important gaps and room for improvement in software and models in literature when it comes to comprehend what makes music alive.

Therefore we present the following hypothesis:

Humanising functions for electronic music production can be improved by fluctuations in both time and energy, acknowledging that different drummers make use of different patterns to induce groove.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter discusses the methodology adopted to perform the rhythmic analysis on our dataset. First, the ENST-Drums, an extensive database for drums signal processing, is described; then the dataset's challenges to overcome the related restrictions are presented. Moreover, the timing and the dynamics measurements necessary for the rhythmic analysis are detailed.

3.1 The dataset: ENST-Drums

3.1.1 Description of the dataset

The "ENST-Drums: an extensive audio-visual database for drum signals processing" dataset [67], presented at ISMIR 2006 by Olivier Gillet and Gaël Richard, has been used for the purposes of rhythmic analysis of this thesis. Three professional drummers (Louis Cavé, Bertrand Clouard and Frédéric Rottier)¹ recorded about 225 minutes of different drum sequences in various styles (bossa, disco, afro, reggae, jazz, swing, salsa, cha-cha, oriental, rock, blues, metal, hard rock, waltz, funk, country). The dataset, which is for free for research purposes, contains eight audio channels for each track, video recordings and complete onset annotations as

¹The dataset does not include further information about the drummers. Following an online research, Cavé appears to be a jazz musician; Clouard is a member of an orchestra; no information on Rottier and his preferred styles could be found.

.txt-files. Various factors make this dataset an apt choice for our research purposes:

- a wide array of recorded phrases (between 10 and 30 seconds long) and solos (from 30 to 80 seconds).
- sixteen styles available, nine styles are common to all three drummers
- each style comports six variations of a phrase, classified into three different tempi (slow, medium, fast) and complexity level: straight (without ornaments) and complex (with ornaments and fill-ins).
- each drummer used his own drum kit, thus everything from a small, portable, kit with two toms and 2 cymbals to a larger rock drum set with 4 toms and 5 cymbals is played.
- semi-automated onset annotations with specified instruments from the authors available.

The six different instrument annotation categories can be found in figure 7 - the proposed classification of instrument groups has been adopted for the rhythmic analysis part:

3.1.2 Challenges of the dataset

The ENST-Drums dataset brought with several obstacles too:

- although nine styles are common to all three drummers, only four have been performed by all three drummers: disco, rock, afro, shuffle blues. This is an important restriction of the dataset we have to be aware for producing hypotheses in a later stage.
- the original paper [67] offers only a vague description of the dataset's content, so further statistics had to be computed separately (for instance, number of onsets, used instruments per track, instrument ratio).

Table 2. Labels used in the annotation

Label	Description	Label	Description
bd	Bass drum	lmt	Low-mid tom
sweep	Brush sweep	mt	Mid tom
sticks	Sticks hit together	mtr	Mid tom, hit on the rim
sd	Snare drum	lt	Low tom
rs	Rim shot	ltr	Low tom, hit on the rim
cs	Cross stick	lft	Lowest tom
chh	Hi-hat (closed)	rc	Ride cymbal
ohh	Hi-hat (open)	ch	Chinese ride cymbal
cb	Cowbell	cr	Crash cymbal
c	Other cymbals	spl	Splash cymbal

Figure 7: Labels used in the ENST-Drums dataset

- the tracks were not recorded along a click-track nor were the first downbeats of the songs annotated, so building a metrical grid mimicking a metronome and selecting the correct beats were a challenge.

Due to this lack of information, an additional step of data pre-processing had to be taken.

3.1.3 Data pre-processing

Due to limited scope of this research project, only tracks in binary metre (4/4) were retained. Since the annotated onset files did not include information about the first and last downbeat, this information was retrieved using SonicVisualiser and finding the corresponding onset in the ground truth. Furthermore, the number of beats for each track respectively was counted by listening to the track. The number of beats and the downbeats were then used to construct an idealised metrical grid.

3.2 Measurement process

3.2.1 Timing Analysis

Defining a metrical grid

A crucial step towards measuring the micro-timing deviations is to define an idealised metrical grid as a reference, i.e. to have an imaginary metronome playing along the track. For the ENST-dataset (and so in many other recording situations), the drummers did not record their phrases along a metronome click track, thus a natural shift of tempo can be found. Räsänen called this observation the *"drift"* - *"the deviation from an imaginary metronome during the song"*. Drift-related graphs for each track can be found in the online repository (see Appendix B).

A metrical grid was created using the information from the pre-processing step: first downbeat, last downbeat, beat count. As only tracks in binary metre (4/4) were retained, the deviations can be visualised on 4 beats formed by 4 sixteenths each, giving us 16 steps of ideal sixteenths in total. The first and last downbeat have been defined as the 0-deviation of steps 1 and 13 and the remaining 14 steps were defined as a grid with equally spaced lines (cf. figure 8). Then, the ground truth onsets are plotted against the idealised metrical grid, as seen in figure 9.

Working with a time resolution of sixteenths notes has been a classical approach to sequencers - furthermore, on an academic level, Räsänen [62] has shown that long-range correlations in the fluctuations of time and energy become apparent on the level of sixteenths.

Other approaches to define a metrical grid have been proposed in literature: Marchini says that the metrical grid can *"be elastic in the sense that, up to a certain degree, it adapts to the timing of the actual sequence"* [68]. However, we have decided against this step because of multiple reasons: important ground truth information is missing; no beat annotations were provided with the dataset; no tempo annotation provided with the dataset as it was not recorded to a click-track. We have

attempted to automate these steps, however, both the Essentia tempo estimation and beat tracker algorithm's performances were too influenced by the drift of each song and were not a reliable grid to measure the micro-timing deviations against.

Visualisation of deviations: heatmaps

Each ideal sixteenth is a fixed time mark, from which the ground truth occurrences of onsets are measured and the time difference quantified.

To visualise the deviations of the onsets from the ideal isochronous divisions of the beats, we have opted for heatmaps, as seen in figure 10: each ideal sixteenth in itself is a 0; deviations are shown on a discretised time scale (resolution of 5 milliseconds around 0, then of 10 milliseconds) on the y-axis: the real onsets are either anticipated (negative time) or delayed (positive time) with respect to the ideal sixteenth. This process is repeated for all 16 steps, each column of the heatmap representing one step. Outliers of the range -100 to 100 milliseconds have been ignored. As Davies suggested, micro-timing deviations of 5 or less milliseconds are indistinguishable, therefore, they have their own category on the y-axis. [7]

3.2.2 Dynamics analysis

Dynamics have many different definitions in musical context. For the purpose of this research project focused on drums, we will assume Räsänen's definition: "*the amplitudes—or dynamics in drumming terminology*" [62]. Further, he states that "*the correlation properties of amplitude (i.e., loudness) fluctuations of beats in rhythms have not been scrutinized as yet*" in academia, thus we attempt to cover more ground here. From an objective point of view, amplitude is the measurement of the degree of change in atmospheric pressure caused by sound waves. In this study, we have used the loudness algorithm implemented in Essentia. It "*computes the loudness of an audio signal defined by Steven's power law*", correlated to the RMS level of signal. The amplitude has been computed for each onset, which are computed and assigned to an ideal sixteenth step as described in 3.2.

(a) Annotating downbeats

(b) Idealised beats

(c) Idealised sixteenths

Figure 8: Defining a metrical grid

Figure 9: Actual onset against idealised metrical grid

Figure 10: Actual onset against idealised metrical grid

3.2.3 Discussion

For the purpose of this research, 18 tracks (6 per genre) per drummer have been annotated and heatmaps for energy and time created. All of the graphs can be found in the online repository (see Appendix B). The 54 songs vary by tempo, ornamentation, genre and overall drumming style, therefore various dimensions of our dataset will be discussed in the rhythmic analysis that follows in the next chapter.

Chapter 4

Rhythmic Analysis

This chapter applies the aforementioned methodology for rhythmic analysis to the selected dataset in order to formulate relevant hypotheses, compare them against findings from literature and validate them through further statistical analysis. First, we comment on the respective time heatmaps for drummers, genres and instrument groups. Then, we take a look at the energy heatmaps for drummers and genres. The partial hypotheses are then validated through machine learning approaches. Finally, results from literature are compared against our findings.

4.1 Interpreting the heatmaps: time

Heatmaps are the most effective way to visualise our findings and to investigate, compare and improve our understanding on genres, drummers and the different behaviours of each instrument. Yet, the visualisation is not sufficient for the formulation of relevant hypotheses about possible correlations or dependencies. In order to unravel these unseen structures, we additionally make use of clustering algorithms, namely: k-Means, AP-Clustering, Hierarchical Clustering and DBSCAN.

Clustering

The main difference between the k-Means and Affinity Propagation clustering is how the number of clusters is determined. In the former algorithm, that number is

determined by the user; techniques such as the silhouette method can be used to find the amount where the clusters are separated best. The latter algorithm determines the best number of clusters for the given dataset itself. Additionally, it outputs an exemplar, e.g. the most representative of the other samples, for each cluster.

The third clustering algorithm in that category is the DBSCAN algorithm. Unlike the k-Means algorithm, its clusters are not convex-shaped, but can take any form. As we aim to discover the underlying patterns on the level of sixteenth steps and beats, this algorithm was not well suited.

When run to find patterns on a step- and beat-level, both the AP-clustering as well as the k-Means clustering in the case of drummer1 found the exact same amount of clusters. As the former algorithm provides additional information, we have opted to only run AP-clustering on our complete dataset.

Furthermore, to gain a better understanding of the construction of each cluster and the similarity space between each step, we have used the Hierarchical Clustering algorithm. It outputs a dendrogram, where the y-axis defines measures the closeness of individual data points or clusters. That way, we are able to gain more knowledge on the similarity of different steps.

4.1.1 Drummers

The heatmaps in figure 11 illustrate distinct drumming characteristics for each of the three musicians:

1. drummer3 uses more strokes than the other two drummers
2. the heatmap of drummer2 is the tightest
3. the heatmap of drummer3 is the most spread out, with a tendency for delays

The results of the hierarchical clustering algorithm as seen in figure 12 validate our musical intuition: indeed, the cluster dendrogram completely separates even and odd

(a) Drummer1

(b) Drummer2

(c) Drummer3

Figure 11: Heatmaps for micro-timing deviations for three drummers

Figure 12: Hierarchical clustering of steps

all instruments	# clusters	STEPS															
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
DRUMMER 1	3	X															
DRUMMER 2	4																
DRUMMER 3	5																
		X = exemplar															
		colour = cluster group															

Figure 13: Results of AP Clustering for drummers

steps from each other. Looking at the odd ones, we realise that the first step of beat #1 and #2, as well as the first step of beat # 2 and #3 are closest to each other.

The hypothesis that each of the drummers has a unique drumming style finds further evidence in the AP-clustering analysis, as seen in figure 13: the ideal amount of clusters for the algorithm is different for each of them. Drummer2 and drummer3 share the exemplars for the first steps of beat 2, 3 and 4: step 5 which is applied to step 9 as well as step 13. Drummer1 and drummer2 share the same exemplars for step 1 of beat 1, for all even steps as well as for step 15. Thus the drummers show similar behaviour in some as well as differences in other steps.

4.1.2 Genre

In this subsection, we focus on two genres, as throughout the dataset, they consistently feature a 4/4 beat : *rock* and *disco*. In a similar way to the heatmaps of the drummers, these heatmaps show distinct characteristics. As expected, the "*disco*" genre is much tighter than the "*rock*" genre. This phenomenon is especially true in the case of drummer 2, but like-wise in the cases of drummer 1 and 3, where the heatmaps are less spread out for "*disco*" than for "*rock*". For the style of "*disco*", we observe that the first step of each beat has the highest amount of strokes - generally

speaking, most patterns for "*disco*" could be classified on the level of 8th notes. Furthermore, for "*disco*" of drummer 2, we observe a tendency to stay close to the idealised metronome, validating once more the commonly associated "tight" feel of the genre.

Additionally, in the hierarchical clustering for genres, we observe, that, in the case of disco, the first steps of each beat are separated from the rest of the 12 other steps and thus share a similar behaviour. This is not the case for the "*rock*" genre, therefore we can conclude that steps 1, 5, 9 and 13 are one important element when trying to classify the styles of disco-tracks. For "*rock*", we observe that odd and even steps are completely separated - this steady oscillation between two states can be interpreted as one possible reason for the energy usually associated with rock performances.

4.1.3 Instruments

Various observations on the distinct behaviour for each instrument group can be made when looking at the heatmaps:

- in all three cases, the bass drum is most prominent on the first step of each beat: indeed, the kick in 4/4 songs is commonly used by drummers to mark the beat. In the case of drummer2, we observe a tendency for anticipation, whereas drummer3 offers a tendency towards delaying the first beat on the kick. The heatmap of drummer1 suggests an oscillatory movement, which stands in line with the push-pull feeling of groove mentioned in our literature review.
- the hi-hat complements the bass drum by being most prominent on the first and third step of each beat.
- the patterns of the snare are different for each drummer: drummer2 emphasises on the first step of beat 2 and 4, whereas drummer3 appears to use his hi-hats throughout all sixteen steps.

Figure 14: Heatmaps for micro-timing deviations for genre disco (left) and rock (right)

Figure 15: Hierarchical clustering of genres; disco (left), rock (right)

Figure 16: Micro-timing deviations for instruments of drummer1

- no clear pattern for the cymbal emerges across the three drummers, however, drummer3 tends to be late on odd steps with his cymbals.
- the heatmaps for the toms are populated mostly towards beat 4, which indicates how this instrument groups is mainly used for fills at the end of the phrases.

4.2 Interpreting the heatmaps: energy

The heatmaps for energy fluctuation confirm our first musical intuition: emphasis lies on the first and third step of each beat. This way, a drummer ensures the perception of a regular beat for the other musicians and the audience. On an individual base, we see that drummer1 and drummer3 have the tendency to strike the first step harder than the third step, thereby signalling the start of each beat. For drummer2 on the other hand, we observe a very consistent pattern between 10 and 30 (the unit for amplitude is arbitrary).

Furthermore, we computed the heatmaps for drummer1 for the genres "*rock*" and "*disco*". We observe that the first steps of the odd beats 2 and 4 are important to the genre "*disco*". In comparison, the "*rock*" genre suggests a more constant and - more importantly - a louder pattern.

Figure 17: Micro-timing deviations for instruments of drummer2

Figure 18: Micro-timing deviations for instruments of drummer3

Figure 19: Amplitude fluctuations for all instruments for drummer1, drummer2 and drummer3

Figure 20: Amplitude fluctuations for "disco" and "rock" - drummer 1

The heatmaps for energy confirm many of our musical intuitions. Furthermore, we see that the amplitude fluctuations are linked to each drummer's style. However, the results are not as distinct as the micro-timing deviations nor have amplitude fluctuations been treated extensively in literature, so we see ourselves unable to comment on possible hypotheses. Due to the limited scope of this thesis, we have therefore decided to only focus on time variations for the remainder of this thesis. For future work and the integration of energy fluctuations in a groove system, we would suggest the creation of an algorithm that generates amplitude patterns in the form of a sixteen step time-series.

4.3 Classification

After the clustering stage, we have tried classification patterns to obtain further validation for our hypotheses on micro-timing deviations. Three major claims are investigated:

- each drummer's style is unique
- instrument categories have distinct behaviour
- genres can be recognised based on micro-timing patterns [43] [7]

For this task, three popular classification algorithm implementations from the sci-kit learn Python library have been used: Support Vector Machines, Nearest Neighbour and Random Forest.

In all three cases, results have been rather underwhelming and will be discussed as follows.

All three algorithms show a low accuracy of between 33 and 36 percent for recognising each drummer; however, an interesting pattern emerged. Drummer1 has been recognised in all of the case, drummer 3 sporadically and drummer2 not at all. As discussed in the point on clustering, we see that drummer2 shared similar characteristics with both drummer1 and drummer3, but drummer1 and drummer3 did not share any similarities. Therefore, we might assume that drummer2's behaviour is a hybrid between drummer1 and drummer3.

The highest result achieved for instrument classification was 33 percent in the case of a support vector machine with a poly kernel. The plot below shows the confusion matrix constructed for that case. We see that snares are the instrument with the highest classification scores and cymbals the one with the lowest. No apparent pattern or recurring confusion can be detected in this confusion matrix, therefore we must conclude that the instruments are not distinct enough to be classified according to their category.

		POLY				
DRUMMER1						
	Hi-Hat	1	13	2	0	
	Bass	3	12	1	0	
	Snare	2	4	10	0	
	Cymbals	1	12	3	0	
DRUMMER2						
	Hi-Hat	6	3	6	1	
	Bass	3	7	4	2	
	Snare	4	6	3	3	
	Cymbals	4	4	7	1	
DRUMMER3						
	Hi-Hat	8	3	5	0	
	Bass	5	3	7	1	
	Snare	2	3	11	0	
	Cymbals	2	5	8	1	

Figure 21: Instrument classification: SVM with poly kernel

The best result for the classification task was achieved for genre detection. In all three algorithms, the score is above 50 percent: for nearest neighbour, it is 60 percent, for random forest 53 and for the Support Vector Machine 71 percent. Therefore, the hypothesis that genres "rock" and "disco" have unique micro-timing deviation patterns - as deduced from our heatmap patterns - has been validated by our statistical analysis.

Thus, apart from genre classification, our classification methods have not achieved results as high as expected. Reasons may be manifold: not enough samples were fed to the classifier, not the best suited classification approach was chosen, or after all, our original data is not distinct enough to be classified into three, in the case of the drummers, or five, in the case of the instrument groups, different classes.

Classification	SVM	Nearest Neighbour	Random Forest
Drummer	36%	33%	33%
Genre	71%	60%	53%
Instrument	33%	30%	30%

Table 1: Overview of results

4.4 Validation of Hypotheses

The following section comments on further hypotheses regarding micro-timing deviations and real-life drumming, extracted from the literature detailed in chapter 2. It is treated as a separate section as no machine learning approaches were used.

- deviations depend on tempo: deviations get smaller as the tempo increases [43]

	slow	fast	total strokes
drummer1	17.6	7.08	[125:127]
drummer2	6.32	5.03	[174:179]
drummer3	19.35	13.55	[155:214]

Table 2: Deviations getting smaller with time

Since the heatmaps of the *"rock"*-genre are more spread out than the *"disco"*-genre, we have opted to test this hypothesis by comparing the slow and fast *"rock"*-tracks of each drummer. We compared the percentage of strokes that lie outside the range -0.06 to 0.06 seconds and have been able to confirm Bilmes' hypothesis. Indeed, all three of the drummers, as can be seen in table ??, have a higher percentage of strokes outside of the defined range in the slower than in the faster tracks.

Indeed, each of the three drummers has a higher percentage of strokes outside of the defined range: for the drummer2, the difference is only of 1.29 percent, but for drummers 1 and 3, the difference is over 10 percent. Therefore, we can assume that the micro-timing deviations for the genre of **"rock"** and the case of the three drummers depend on the tempo.

DRUMMER1	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10	#11	#12	#13	#14	#15	#16	TOTAL	
SNARE	-0.078	0.002	0.017	0.014	0.015	-0.025	0.003	0.005	-0.016	0.013	0.023	-0.007	0.01	-0.003	0	-0.003		
BASS	DRUM	0.006	-0.034	0.005	-0.002	0.004	-0.02	0.001	0.019	0.004	-0.001	0.012	-0.007	0	0.01	-0.002		
difference		-0.084	0.036	0.012	0.016	0.011	-0.005	0.002	-0.014	-0.02	0.014	0.01	0	0.011	-0.013	0.002	-0.003	-0.0016
DRUMMER2																		
SNARE	-0.001	-0.003	-0.02	0.021	0.01	-0.019	-0.014	0.026	0.001	0.002	-0.005	0.023	0.009	-0.009	-0.004	0.026		
BASS	DRUM	0.001	-0.024	0.022	-0.032	-0.007	-0.022	0.011	-0.023	0.002	0.007	0.015	-0.035	-0.002	0.006	0.015		
difference		-0.003	0.02	-0.043	0.053	0.017	0.003	-0.025	0.05	-0.001	-0.005	-0.019	0.058	0.011	-0.015	-0.02	0.053	0.0084
DRUMMER3																		
SNARE	-0.007	0.009	-0.002	0	0.008	0.004	-0.005	0.008	-0.011	0.01	0.001	0.013	0.017	0.003	0.003	0.001		
BASS	DRUM	0.005	-0.016	-0.005	-0.011	0.006	-0.013	-0.008	0.003	0.012	-0.006	-0.017	-0.004	0.007	0	0		
difference		-0.012	0.026	0.003	0.011	0.003	0.017	0.002	0.005	-0.023	0.016	0.017	0.017	0.01	0.003	0.003	0.014	0.007

Figure 22: Time difference between snare drum and bass drum per drummer

- the snare drum is struck slightly later than the bass drum [5] [12]

In order to validate this hypothesis, we have calculated the average micro-timing deviation for each step. Then we took the difference between the averages of the snare drum and the bass drum. Results are detailed in figure 22. We are able to see that for drummer2 and drummer3 Iyer's and Butterfield's observation are proven, whereas for drummer1, the bass drum is minimally later than the snare drum, which may be due to the fact that each drummer has their unique drumming style.

- microtiming shifts between 10 and 30 ms are a reasonable range [5]

Although Butterfield explicitly defines these micro-timing shifts for jazz music, we cannot find evidence for this claim in our data. In table 3, we observe that for all three drummers, less than 35% of the deviations (0 and 5 milliseconds excluded) are within the time range of [-30:-10; 10:30] milliseconds.

- anticipation of third and fourth 16th in a beat (specifically for samba [7] [34])

We have computed the median (rather than the average, as it is less influenced by outliers) of the quantised micro-timing deviations of each drummer for the third and fourth step of each beat, the results can be seen in table 4. We are unable to observe a clear towards anticipation in the drummer's behaviour. Of all three drummers, drummer2 shows the most signs for anticipation, therefore we compute the median for the styles of drummer 2 separately, as seen in table 5. We cannot find a distinct pattern for anticipation, therefore we assume that the hypothesis is specific to genres

step	drummer1	drummer2	drummer3
1	29.2	28.5	31.5
2	41.3	29.2	37.7
3	43.5	35.5	35.9
4	14.8	29.3	35.6
5	52.2	30.5	35.3
6	12.9	36.0	27
7	40.9	31.9	41.1
8	27.0	30.8	32.7
9	42.2	35.4	34.5
10	32.2	38.7	35.2
11	47.6	35.8	42.6
12	19.4	26	25.7
13	31.2	27.8	31.8
14	29.3	35.8	28.6
15	43.7	35.2	41.3
16	29.5	26	29.4
Average	33.6	32	34.1

Table 3: Percentage of micro-timing deviations within the range of -30 to -10 and 10 to 30 milliseconds

outside our study, such as samba, the original study case of Naveda.

step	drummer1	drummer2	drummer3
3	5	-5	5
4	0	-10	-10
7	5	0	5
8	20	0	5
11	10	0	-5
12	0	-5	0
15	0	0	0
16	10	-5	-5

Table 4: Median of quantised micro-timing deviations

step	disco	rock
3	-10	-5
4	0	-20
7	-10	-5
8	60	20
11	-20	0
12	5	-20
15	-10	0
16	20	50

Table 5: Median of quantised micro-timing deviations for styles of drummer2

Chapter 5

Generative groove system

This chapter details the implementation and a proof of concept of a generative groove system, based on our previous findings.

5.1 Concept

The system has been written in PureData, a visual programming language for interactive computer music, and the *"extended"* distribution. PureData allows for the creation of an easily operable stand-alone application, which can be used and improved by any computer owner. Furthermore, its free and open-source philosophy since its creation in 1996 has attracted an active online community, which constantly

Figure 23: Scheme of our generative groove system

Figure 24: Main pd-patch of groove system

releases add-ons, some of them being of use for our project.

The system we present now is a 16-step sequencer (cf. figure 23) reflecting the fluctuations in time deduced from our prior analysis. This way, the user can operate the sequencer like a standard drum machine, while a generative system in the background creates micro-timing deviations, based on the behaviour of real-life drummers, in real-time.

5.2 System prototype

We will now explain the different parts of the PureData-patch:

Step-Sequencer

The patch represents a standard 16-step sequencer, where sounds at each step can be programmed and triggered by clicking on the corresponding toggle. In the patch "*pd drum-machine-patterns*", various famous drum machine patterns are pre-programmed and accessible through one click to give the user some reference rhythms for a quick start. When opening the patch, six sounds retrieved from the famous Roland TR-707 drum machine are loaded into the sequencer: kick drum, snare drum 1, snare drum 2, closed hi-hat, open hi-hat and cymbal. The sub-patch "*pd instruments*" offers the possibility to load the user's own sounds into the patch and visualise them in an array.

Metro/Clock

At the heart of this patch is the metronome, which triggers the sound events and moves through the different steps of our sequencer. The metronome is flexible and can delay or anticipate events with respect to a rigid pulse. In our system, we make use of the object *metroplus* from the "*mjlib*" library. This object, by Mark Williamson, is a variation of the metro object and allows for an irregular beat rather than a steady pulse. A sequence of numbers can be sent to the right inlet of the object, where the numbers represent the intervals in milliseconds. The sequence our patch sends to *metroplus* is generated in the "*pd metro*" sub-patch. For each step, we have extracted a probability curve from the relevant heatmaps. This information is stored in a message and after the completion of each cycle of the step sequencer, a new number representing a new micro-timing deviation is being output. This is done for all sixteen steps. Then a number representing the inter-onset interval for the selected BPM is added - the default being set at 600 milliseconds, representing 100 bpm. The resulting output is stored in a list. This list is sent in a message to the *metroplus* object, which triggers events according to the previously generated sequence. The sequence is renewed each time a cycle of 16 steps is finished. The sub-patch "*pd metro*" is then applied to each of the instruments with the corresponding probability curves extracted from the rhythmic analysis of three real-life drummers

Figure 25: Sound presets in subpatch "pd instruments"

Figure 26: Probability tables and number selection in sub-patch "pd metro"

in the previous chapter.

As the sequence within the patch is only created by independent probability curves and thus ignores important relationships between the different steps, we have opted to write an algorithm outside of PureData, which creates different fluctuation patterns, which can then be fed back to our system.

5.3 Pattern generation

Building on the positive results concerning genre recognition from the previous chapter, we have developed a basic algorithm to generate new patterns for each genre. For each of the sixteen steps, the algorithm reads in the respective probability curve, deduced from the genre-specific heatmap. A random choice function outputs a new number based on the probability curve. We have improved that random choice function by defining dependencies between steps. To do so, we make use of our AP-clustering analysis results, where steps were regrouped in clusters, with an exemplar per cluster defined. That way, our algorithm calculates a deviation value for each of the exemplars; then, for all steps linked to that specific exemplar, a random value is calculated that has to lie within a maximum, bipolar deviation from the exemplar. The algorithm is controlled by two parameters: first, this maximum deviation from

	Disco	Rock	Disco 4+ series	Rock 4+ series
<i>Drummer1</i>	0.908	0.656	0.925	0.775
	Average:	<i>0.782</i>	Average 4+ series:	<i>0.850</i>
<i>Drummer2</i>	0.916	0.531	0.839	0.963
	Average:	<i>0.724</i>	Average 4+ series:	<i>0.901</i>
<i>Drummer3</i>	0.919	0.540	0.925	0.646
	Average:	<i>0.730</i>	Average 4+ series:	<i>0.785</i>

Table 6: Train/Test Results for generated patterns

the exemplar in milliseconds; secondly, a number of cycles of sixteen steps, which the algorithm should complete. The output of the algorithm is a newly generated micro-timing deviations pattern based on prior genre-specific rhythmic analysis of each drummer.

To ensure that the newly generated patterns can be classified according to genre, we apply machine learning techniques: we train a support vector machine for each drummer with instances from the "*rock*" and "*disco*" genre and test the newly generated pattern against the model. About 70 patterns, with varying parameters for the cycles, for each drummer were generated in total. We observe that patterns with multiple series perform better, therefore we present our findings in table 6 in two steps: one summarising results for all patterns and one for patterns formed by at least 4 cycles.

In all six resulting categories, our classification performs with an accuracy of over 70 percent; even reaching 90 percent in case of drummer2 and more than 4 series. Furthermore, we observe that the longer series perform better in every single test case. As we have seen before, an important difference between "*rock*" and "*disco*" lies in how far their heatmaps are spread out. We must note though that the probability curves of "*disco*" contain spread out values as well, therefore a randomly generated pattern with 16 steps could still be confused with a "*rock*" pattern. Increasing the number of cycles increases the probability of generating more genre-specific sequences.

In a second step, to validate our proof of concept for the generative groove system, we perform a cross-validation.

For this purpose, we choose K-fold cross-validation, a systematic process for repeating the train/test split procedure from step one multiple times. Our complete dataset of instances - both from real-life recordings and the generation algorithms is split into K equal folds (or partitions). The first fold is used as a test set and the other folders are put together to form a training set. Then, the accuracy of performance with the given model is calculated. These two steps are repeated K times, using a different fold as test set every time. This way, we ensure that every data point is tested exactly once and is used for training K-1 times. Then, the average of the K accuracies is computed. Although being computationally more expensive than the train/test split, the results we get from the K-fold cross-validation allow us to check how well our models generalise to new data. Besides smoothing out any bias towards the test set, the K-fold cross validation gives us freedom over the size of the latter.

We have performed K-fold cross-validation with changing values for K (from 2 to 100) and three classifiers (Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, K Neighbours). In order to further reduce possible bias, we average the result of five iterations for each case. This step is performed with the *shuffleSplit* function from the *scikit-learn* library, to ensure further randomness of training and test sets.

The final evaluation results for the three classifiers can be found in tables 7,8,9. The average for each model lies between 70 and 77 percent. In each case, varying the number of k-folds does not affect as much as could have been expected. Indeed, we are not able to find a soft spot for improving the parameters of our classifiers. Nonetheless, the results from the cross-validation process provide a proof of concept of our generative groove system.

In this chapter, we have presented a musical groove system and a algorithm for the generation of micro-timing deviation sequences. Through a cross-validation process, these sequences have been classified according to their genre with over 70% accuracy. We have thus been able to provide a proof of concept that both our classification methods as well as the generative groove system are working well.

<i>k-folds</i>	SVM	K-Neighbour	Random Forest
2	79.80	68.40	76.90
3	79.20	72.50	74.10
4	76.90	67.90	74.10
5	75.30	70.60	73.60
10	77.50	71.20	75.70
40	77.20	70.50	75.20
60	77.00	69.80	75.30
80	77.00	70.00	75.30
100	77.10	70.30	75.60
<i>Average</i>	<i>77.44</i>	<i>70.13</i>	<i>75.09</i>

Table 7: Cross-validation results for drummer 1

<i>k-folds</i>	SVM	K-Neighbour	Random Forest
2	76.7	72.8	74.4
3	72.5	73.2	74.4
4	76.7	74	74
5	78.2	72.4	75.7
10	76.5	73.6	74
40	76.2	73.2	75.3
60	76.8	72.6	75.6
80	76.8	73.3	75.1
100	77	72.7	75.7
<i>Average</i>	<i>74.91</i>	<i>73.09</i>	<i>74.91</i>

Table 8: Cross-validation results for drummer 2

<i>k-folds</i>	SVM	K-Neighbour	Random Forest
2	75.3	72.5	75
3	76.5	72.6	75.7
4	76.2	73.7	74.1
5	75.4	72.4	78
10	77.1	72.1	74.8
40	77.36	72.1	75.7
60	77.15	73.4	75.5
80	76.6	73.3	75.3
100	77.3	73.2	75.7
<i>Average</i>	<i>75.53</i>	<i>72.81</i>	<i>75.53</i>

Table 9: Cross-validation results for drummer 3

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Future Work

This chapter will provide ideas for future work and summarises our findings about drum groove analysis and generation.

6.1 Future Work

In this section, we will provide pointers towards future work related to our research question.

System evaluation methodology

This thesis has given proof of concept that a humanising function can be modelled according to genres. The next step would involve subjects interacting with the musical groove system - we therefore propose an evaluation methodology for this system now. Two qualities should be sought after for an expert evaluation of the system: users with experience in drumming and/or experience in music production. This way, we guarantee familiarity with either the real-life behaviour of drummers or the limitations of current humanising functions in digital audio workstations.

The first part would encompass the evaluation of the real-life drummers and their recordings in the ENST-Drums dataset. In this thesis, their behaviour is only modelled and compared to literature findings, however, they have not been accessed on

their *"groove"*.

We have to be aware that every user has made their own abstraction of what groove means. A possible evaluation could rely on the definition commonly used in academic experiments: groove incites the need for dancing. We, however, would like to further investigate on differences of perception in what sounds *"natural"*, *"human"*, *"good"* or *"groovy"* to each user. A possible study related to those terms could involve the original drum sequence, a quantised drum sequence, the latter randomised by a Gaussian distribution, and the drum sequence generated with our system. This approach could evaluate the model of each of the three drummers.

A study of the models of the genres could be done by adopting the pre-programmed patterns, as well as adopting the drum kit and drum sounds to the iconic features of the respective style; then asking the user whether it sounds *"natural"* or *"human"* to them.

Due to its design as a step sequencer, the proposed system allows for a certain degree of interaction - a more time-consuming task for the user could involve playfully exploring the system and notating the *"grooviness"* of each sequence. Moving into an even more experimental area, we could imagine the construction of a 2-D probability space for evaluation purposes. The probability curves of each drummer could be fed in, and an interpolation algorithm applied to make the probability space continuous. The user could then navigate through that space and choose the sequences that sound *"most natural"*, *"most human"*, *"best"*, or *"grooviest"*. We could then compare it to our real-life data and evaluate whether the user prefers a specific drumming behaviour or a hybrid behaviour.

As we have seen, the approaches for evaluating our system are manifold: additionally, an evaluation would be needed to deepen our understanding of groove in the context of the system and enhance our algorithms for pattern generation.

Analysis with more data

This thesis does not cover the entirety of tracks provided by the ENST-Drums dataset, as we have focused on songs with binary metre and performed by all three drummers. Our analysis could be extended to various other genres (afro, funk, waltz to name but a few) as well as annotated solo-performances with a duration of over one minute. That way, a better understanding of the behaviour of each drummer in different situations, but also of different genres could be gained. Furthermore, our findings could be compared to commercial recordings of drummers to see whether similarities between drummers can be found and characteristics of different styles confirmed.

Analysis of interlocking

In this project, we have treated the drums isolated from any other instrument. A future step would be to analyse the interlocking of the rhythm section (bass and drums) and, eventually, the interlocking of the rhythm section with the melodic section. This would enable the unraveling of another level of groove creation. Moreover, it would allow us to build a interactive system, which analyses the audio input from the user and adapts the fluctuations in timing and dynamics to the user's behaviour.

Rhythm generation

Promising research on rhythm generation has been undertaken over the course of this year [63]. A genre-specific rhythm generator could substitute the step sequencer at the core of our system and add another degree of generation to it.

Groove spaces

On the basis of timbre spaces REFERENCE and rhythm spaces REFERENCE, a groove space could be proposed. Various dimensions of groove have been identified in chapter 2, of which two (energy and time) have been analysed in this thesis. A complex, non-linear space could be defined by taking into account these descriptors and weighting the components based on their importance. One possible application

of that space would be a new visual classification of commonly used groove patterns (available in various digital audio workstations): that way, a visual space to browse through grooves could be created, improving on the non-intuitive click-through list presented in current DAWs, further improving the workflow of electronic music producers.

6.2 Conclusions

This thesis has investigated the analysis and generation of groove in real-life drum recordings: by complementing perceptual observations about rhythm and groove with the computational analysis of musical recordings of real-life drummers, a generative groove system has been implemented.

Analysing the ENST-Drums dataset, we were able to confirm or comment on various hypotheses from literature on the subject of drummers. Furthermore, the analysis enabled us to understand groove and the drummers' behaviour better on a step- and beat-level. This thesis has been a proof of concept that:

- We can understand groove better and build more natural, multi-dimensional computer-based systems.
- Genres can be characterised and classified by their micro-timing patterns.

Our main contributions are:

- an extensive state-of-the-art on groove, swing and syncopation
- a literature overview on micro-timing deviations
- downbeat annotations of ENST-drums dataset
- detailed rhythmical analysis of three drummers and different genres
- statistical analysis of the ENST-Drums dataset, both for time and energy
- a generative algorithm to create new, genre-specific micro-timing deviation patterns

- a prototype of a generative groove system

Moreover, our musical groove system and the generative algorithm have been proven to be well-trained and responsive: an evaluation methodology has been proposed to assess the user experience in the future.

The reproducibility of our work is guaranteed: besides all steps being detailed in this report, the codes for the rhythmical analysis and generative algorithm are available in an online repository. For more details, please refer to Appendices.

We hope that our work will provide an alternative for music producers to currently available humanisers for electronic music production; additionally, we hope it will be of use for researchers to gain further understanding of fluctuations in time and energy as well as to understand training procedures for classification and the sizes of the corpus to be used and analysed.

On a personal level, this thesis has been an educative travel through music history, from the 1950s to the noughties; a journey into the netherworld of rhythm and groove. I have been able to see and understand music from a different perspective, yet I believe that there is much more to be said and discovered about groove than could ever be written in a single thesis.

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Appendix A

Micro-timing deviations

As part of this thesis, an extensive research on micro-timing deviations in literature was undertaken and the result stored in an excel-table. It deals with the following categories: definition of micro-deviation, purpose of study, styles examined, experiment set-up, experiment hypothesis, experiment participants, experiment stimuli, experiment results. Incorporating this table into the final layout of the thesis as well as assuring readability has proven to be impossible. Therefore, we have opted to store our results in the online repository detailed in Appendix B. Meanwhile, we would like to provide the bibliography of this overview on micro-timing deviations:

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Appendix B

Online repository

To complement this project, an online repository has been created. The repository documents all codes used for the completion of this thesis on sound and music computing, thereby guaranteeing reproducibility and a resource for future research on rhythmic analysis, groove and the ENST-Drums dataset.

The repository is organised as follows:

1. **Codes:** The code for this thesis is organised in various jupyter notebooks. The titles of each notebook should be self-explanatory. All code is written in python 2.7., dependencies include: numpy, scipy, matplotlib, scikit-learn, seaborn, Essentia.
2. **Visuals:** Various heatmaps and confusion matrices were not included in this report for readability reasons. All graphs computed for the purpose of this project are included in this folder and can give the interested reader more insight into our findings.
3. **Results:** The detailed results for our classification evaluations can be found in this folder.
4. **Groove system:** This folder contains the patches and sounds needed to build

the generative groove system, self-contained in PureData-extended. Furthermore, it includes the .csv-files of the generated micro-timing patterns.

The repository is accessible through the following link:

<https://github.com/ttroes/measuring-groove>